

KOSHI INTEGRAL TEOREMASI.

Rustamov Bilol

Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti Oliy
matematika kafedrasida o'qituvchi
Rustamovb374@gmail.com

Xonqulov Sherzod

Yangiboyeva Mohira

Choriyeva Nozigul

Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti talabasi.
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ABSTRACT

Biz bu maqolada kompleks analizning asosiy tushunchalaridan biri Koshi teoremasi haqida malumotga ega bo'lamiz va Koshi teoremasini isbotini uchburchak orqali isbotlaymiz va natijalarini ko'ramiz.

1°. Koshi teoremasi kompleks o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar nazariyasining fundamental teoremasi hisoblanadi.

Biz ushbu paragrafda mazkur teoremani o'rganamiz.

2-teorema (Koshi teoremasi). Agar $f(z)$ funksiya bir bog'lamli D sohada $D \subset C_z$ golomorf bo'lsa, u holda $f(z)$ funksiyaning D sohada yotuvchi har qanday silliq (bo'lakli silliq) γ yopiq chiziq (yopiq kontur) bo'yicha integrali nolga teng bo'ladi:

$$\int_{\gamma} f(z) dz = 0.$$

Isbot. Teoremaning isbotini bir necha bosqichda keltiramiz:

Bu uchburchakning perimetri ℓ ga teng bo'lsin. Bu holda teoremani isbotlash uchun teskarisini faraz qilamiz, ya'ni $f(z)$ funksiya bir bog'lamli D sohada golomorf bo'lsa ham bu funksiyaning D sohada yotuvchi ABC uchburchak konturi Δ bo'yicha integrali nolga teng bo'lmasin:

$$\int_{\Delta} f(z) dz \neq 0.$$

Aytaylik

$$\left| \int_{\gamma} f(z) dz \right| = M > 0$$

bo'lsin

$\Delta = ABC$ uchburchakni uning tomonlari o'rtalarini birlashtiruvchi to'g'ri chiziq kesimlari yordamida 4 ta

$$\Delta^{(1)}, \Delta^{(2)}, \Delta^{(3)}, \Delta^{(4)}$$

Uchburchaklarga ajratamiz. Ravshanki bu uchburchak konturlari uchun

$$\Delta^{(1)} = aB + Bc + ca,$$

$$\Delta^{(2)} = cA + Ab + bc,$$

$$\Delta^{(3)} = bC + Ca + ab$$

$$\Delta^{(4)} = ac + cb + ba$$

bo'lib

$$\int_{\Delta^{(1)}} f(z) dz = \int_{aB} f(z) dz + \int_{Bc} f(z) dz + \int_{ca} f(z) dz,$$

$$\int_{\Delta^{(2)}} f(z) dz = \int_{cA} f(z) dz + \int_{Ab} f(z) dz + \int_{bc} f(z) dz,$$

$$\int_{\Delta^{(3)}} f(z) dz = \int_{bC} f(z) dz + \int_{Ca} f(z) dz + \int_{ab} f(z) dz,$$

$$\int_{\Delta^{(4)}} f(z) dz = \int_{ac} f(z) dz + \int_{cb} f(z) dz + \int_{ba} f(z) dz$$

Bo'ladi. Keyingi tengliklarni hadlab qo'shib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Delta^{(1)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(2)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(3)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(4)}} f(z) dz \\ &= \left[\int_{aB} f(z) dz + \int_{Bc} f(z) dz + \int_{ca} f(z) dz + \int_{bc} f(z) dz + \int_{Ca} f(z) dz \right] \\ &+ \left(\int_{ca} f(z) dz + \int_{ac} f(z) dz \right) + \left(\int_{cb} f(z) dz + \int_{ac} f(z) dz \right) \\ &+ \left(\int_{ab} f(z) dz + \int_{ab} f(z) dz \right). \end{aligned}$$

Agar

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{aB} f(z) dz + \int_{Bc} f(z) dz + \int_{cA} f(z) dz + \int_{Ab} f(z) dz + \int_{bC} f(z) dz + \int_{Ca} f(z) dz = \int_{\Delta} f(z) dz, \\ & \int_{ca} f(z) dz + \int_{ac} f(z) dz = 0, \quad \int_{bc} f(z) dz + \int_{cb} f(z) dz = 0, \\ & \int_{ab} f(z) dz + \int_{ba} f(z) dz = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Bolishini etiborga olsak (9) munosabatdan

$$\int_{\Delta} f(z) dz = \int_{\Delta^{(1)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(2)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(3)}} f(z) dz + \int_{\Delta^{(4)}} f(z) dz$$

Ekanligi kelib chiqdi.

Ravshanki,

$$M = \left| \int_{\Delta} f(z) dz \right| \leq \left| \int_{\Delta^{(1)}} f(z) dz \right| + \left| \int_{\Delta^{(2)}} f(z) dz \right| + \left| \int_{\Delta^{(3)}} f(z) dz \right| + \left| \int_{\Delta^{(4)}} f(z) dz \right|$$

Bu tengsizlikning o'ng tomonidagi qo'shiluvchilardan kamida bittasi $\frac{M}{4}$ dan kichik bo'ladi

(aks holda

$$M = \left| \int_{\Delta} f(z) dz \right| < 4 \cdot \frac{M}{4} = M$$

Bo'lib $M < M$ kabi manosiz tengsizlikka kelib qoladi).

Aytaylik,

$$\left| \int_{\Delta_1} f(z) dz \right| \geq \frac{M}{4}$$

Bo'lsin bunda Δ_1 uchburchak $\Delta^{(1)}, \Delta^{(2)}, \Delta^{(3)}, \Delta^{(4)}$ uchburchaklardan biri va uning perimetri $\frac{1}{2^n}$ ga teng.

Endi Δ_1 uchburchak yuqoridagi usul bilan 4 ta $\Delta^{(1)}, \Delta^{(2)}, \Delta^{(3)}, \Delta^{(4)}$ uchburchaklarga ajratamiz. Bu uchburchaklar orasida Δ_2 uchburchak topiladi

$$\left| \int_{\Delta_2} f(z) dz \right| \geq \frac{M}{4^2}$$

Bo'ladi Δ_2 uchburchakning perimetri $\frac{1}{2^2}$ ga teng

Bu jarayonni cheksiz davom ettira boramiz. Natijada

$$\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \Delta_3, \dots, \Delta_n \quad (10)$$

uchburchaklar ketma-ketligi hosil bo'ladi. (10) uchburchaklar ketma-ketligi uchun:

$$\left| \int_{\Delta_n} f(z) dz \right| \geq \frac{M}{4^n} \quad (11)$$

Bo'ladi

Shartga ko'ra $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada holomorf. Demak, son olinganda ham shunday $\delta = \delta(\varepsilon)$ son topiladiki,

$$|z - z_0| < \delta$$

tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha z lar uchun

$$\left| \frac{f(z) - f(z_0)}{z - z_0} - f'(z) \right| < \varepsilon$$

ya'ni

$$|f(z) - f(z_0) - f'(z)(z - z_0)| < \varepsilon \cdot |z - z_0| \quad (13)$$

Bo'ladi

Endi (2) va (4) formulalarga ko'ra

$$\int_{\Delta_n} dz = 0 \quad \int_{\Delta_n} z dz = 0$$

Va n ning yetarlicha katta qiymatida

$$\Delta_n \subset \{z \in C_z : |z - z_0| < \delta\}$$

bo'lishini hamda (13) tengsizlikni e'tiborga olib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Delta_n} f(z) dz \right| &= \left| \int_{\Delta_n} [f(z) - f(z_0) - f'(z)(z - z_0)] dz \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\Delta_n} |[f(z) - f(z_0) - f'(z)(z - z_0)]| < \varepsilon \cdot \int_{\Delta_n} |z - z_0| |dz| < \varepsilon \cdot \frac{l^2}{4^n} \end{aligned}$$

(11) va (14) munosabatlardan

$$\frac{M}{4^n} \leq \left| \int_{\Delta_n} f(z) dz \right| < \varepsilon \cdot \frac{l^2}{4^n}$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi. Demak,

$$M < \varepsilon \cdot l^2$$

Bu tengsizlik $M > 0$ deb qilingan farazga zid (chunki ε — ixtiyoriy musbat son). Ziddiyatlik bo'lmashligi uchun $M = 0$ bo'lishi kerak. Shunday qilib $M = 0$ ya'ni

$$\int_{\Delta} f(z) dz = 0$$

bo'ladi.

$$\gamma = P.$$

Ravshanki, ko'pburchak chekli sondagi uchburchaklarga ajraladi va

$$\int_P f(z) dz$$

integral esa bu uchburchaklar bo'yicha olingan integrallar yig'indisiga teng bo'ladi. Uchburchaklar bo'yicha olingan integrallarning har biri a) holga binoan nolga teng bo'ladi. Binobarin, $f(z)$ funksiyaning ko'pburchak konturi bo'yicha olingan integrali ham nolga teng bo'ladi:

$$\int_P f(z) dz = 0$$

γ egri chiziq ixtiyoriy silliq (bo'lakli silliq) yopiq egri chiziq bo'lsin. Integralning 6-xossasiga ko'ra D sohaga tegishli bo'lgan shunday P ko'pburchak topiladiki,

$$\left| \int_{\gamma} f(z) dz - \int_P f(z) dz \right| < \varepsilon$$

ε — ixtiyoriy musbat son b) holga binoan

$$\int_P f(z) dz = 0$$

Demak

$$\left| \int_{\gamma} f(z) dz \right| < \varepsilon$$

Bundan esa

$$\int_{\gamma} f(z) dz = 0$$

Bo'lishi kelib chiqadi. Teorema isbotlandi.

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